

ISic1315

I.Sicily inscription 1315

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

ash chest

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140808

1. Ὀπωρε[ι]νε χρ[η]στὲ
2. [χ]αῖρε. □ ἔζη-
3. σεσ ἔτη ἴ □ □
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492920

EDCS 39101685

PHI 140808

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0493 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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